

eLife's new publishing model

Damian Pattinson
Executive Director, eLife

Preprints in the Biomedical Sciences

Preprints in Europe PMC

Preprints are:

- Open
- Immediate
- Controlled by authors

Preprints are not:

- Trustworthy
- Curated

Early posting, late reviews

CSH Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory **bioRxiv** THE PREPRINT SERVER FOR BIOLOGY

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bioRxiv posts many COVID19-related papers. A reminder: they have not been formally peer-reviewed and should not guide health-related behavior or be reported in the press as conclusive.

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Adaptation supports short-term memory in a visual change detection task

Brian Hu, Marina E. Garrett, Peter A. Groblewski, Douglas R. Ollerenshaw, Jiaqi Shang, Kate Roll, Sahar Manavi, Christof Koch, Shawn R. Olsen, Stefan Mihalas
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.03.06.977512>
Now published in *PLOS Computational Biology* doi: [10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009246](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009246)

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COVID-19 SARS-CoV-2 preprint on medRxiv and bioRxiv

Subject Area: Neuroscience

Subject Areas: All Articles, Animal Behavior and Cognition, Biochemistry, Biomechanics

Abstract: The maintenance of short-term memories is critical for survival in a dynamically changing world. Previous studies suggest that this memory can be stored in the form of persistent neural activity or using a synaptic mechanism, such as with short-term plasticity. Here, we compare the predictions of these two mechanisms to neural and behavioral measurements in a visual change detection task. Mice were trained to respond to changes in a repeated sequence of natural images while neural activity was recorded using two-photon calcium imaging. We also

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Adaptation supports short-term memory in a visual change detection task

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Version 2 | Published: September 17, 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009246>

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Article	Authors	Metrics	Comments	Media Coverage	Peer Review
Abstract	Author summary				
	Introduction				
	Methods				
	Results				
	Discussion				
	Supporting information				
	Acknowledgments				

Abstract: The maintenance of short-term memories is critical for survival in a dynamically changing world. Previous studies suggest that this memory can be stored in the form of persistent neural activity or using a synaptic mechanism, such as with short-term plasticity. Here, we compare the predictions of these two mechanisms to neural and behavioral measurements in a visual change detection task. Mice were trained to respond to changes in a repeated sequence of natural images while neural activity was recorded using two-photon calcium imaging. We also trained two types of artificial neural networks on the same change detection task as the mice. Following fixed pre-processing using a pretrained convolutional neural network, either a recurrent neural network (RNN) or a feedforward neural network with short-term synaptic depression (STPNet) was trained to the same level of performance as the mice. While both

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Preprints at eLife

- From 2021 we started to exclusively review papers that had been posted as a preprint
- We have also now posted public reviews and evaluations for more than 2000 preprints

eLife's new model

Key changes to editorial & publishing process

- We will publish all manuscripts with reviews and an eLife assessment on the eLife website
- eLife will no longer make accept/reject decisions after review
- Authors choose when to publish a version of record (these are the items that will be sent for indexing)
- Upfront Article Processing Charge (APC) of \$2,000 charged at the point of sending to peer review (rather than the current USD \$3,000 charged at publication)

The new eLife model

Reviewed Preprint

Curation that communicates the editors' and reviewers' assessment of the impact and quality of the science with controlled vocabulary

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Computational and Systems Biology, Neuroscience

A connectome and analysis of the adult *Drosophila* central brain

Louis K Scheffer, C Shan Xu, Michal Januszewski, Zhiyuan Lu, Shin-ya Takemura, Kenneth J Hayworth, Gary B Huang, Kazunori Shinomiya, Jeremy Maltin-Shepard ... Stephen M Plaza + 24 more.

Janella Research Campus, Howard Hughes Medical Institute, United States • Google Research, United States • Life Sciences Centre, Dalhousie University, Canada • Google Research, Google LLC, Switzerland • Institute for Quantitative Biosciences, University of Tokyo, Japan ... + 4 more.

<https://doi.org/10.7555/eLife.57443>

Full text Figures and data Peer review

Abstract

The neural circuits responsible for animal behavior remain largely unknown. We summarize new methods and present the circuitry of a large fraction of the brain of the fruit fly *Drosophila melanogaster*. Improved methods include new procedures to prepare, image, align, segment, find synapses in, and proofread such large data sets. We define cell types, refine computational compartments, and provide an exhaustive atlas of cell examples and types, many of them novel. We provide detailed circuits consisting of neurons and their chemical synapses for most of the central brain. We make the data public and simplify access, reducing the effort needed to answer circuit questions, and provide procedures linking the neurons defined by our analysis with genetic reagents. Biologically, we examine distributions of connection strengths, neural motifs on different scales, electrical consequences of compartmentalization, and evidence that maximizing packing density is an important criterion in the evolution of the fly's brain.

eLife assessment

This is a **landmark** paper that is methodologically **exceptional** - a tour de force - that ties together decades of advances in electron microscopy to produce a dataset of both breadth and extreme technical quality whose very existence will have profound and lasting influence on neuroscience. The atlas of the fruit-fly brain is an invaluable reference for experimentalists and a springboard for theoreticians and modelers. The manuscript is extensive and well-illustrated, and the data, methods and analyses are made available to the community in an exemplary manner. The work represents ambitious, large-scale biological resource generation at its apotheosis.

eLife's editors no longer accept or reject after peer review. Instead they provide an assessment above a consistent vocabulary. [About Editorial assessments.](#)

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Peer reviewed	May 22, 2022
Sent for review	Apr 19, 2022
Preprint posted	Mar 31, 2022

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17 views

Indication that the work was made available as a preprint and reviewed by eLife

Full peer reviews available within the eLife website

Common vocabulary

Significance of Findings	Strength of Evidence
Landmark: Findings with profound implications and widespread influence, which are likely to be of broad interest.	Exceptional: Exemplary use of existing and new methods that establishes new standards for a field.
Fundamental: Findings that substantially advance understanding of important research questions.	Compelling: High quality data and analyses, more rigorous than the current state-of-the-art.
Important: Findings with theoretical or practical implications for multiple subfields.	Convincing: Appropriate and validated methodology in line with current state-of-the-art, with good support for the claims.
Valuable: Findings with theoretical or practical implications for a subfield.	Solid: Uses appropriate methodology, with minor weaknesses.
Useful: Findings with focused importance and scope.	Incomplete: Methodology provides some support for the main claims with some limitations.
None: For findings with no anticipated impact.	Inadequate: Methodology does not provide support for the primary claims.

Reaction

Wojciech Nawrocki
@wjnawrocki

This is absolutely glorious! Move in a great direction by [@eLife](#), the arguments in the article are fascinating.

This is definitely a revolution in the field and I really like it. I will support this change by continuing to review for eLIFE and submitting my papers there.

Best regards
Sepand

Richard Sever
@cshperspectives

Massive news: eLife to abolish accept/reject decisions: papers will just be “peer reviewed”. Others can argue about this, but lots of interesting consequences. 1/9

elisa fadda
@ElisaTelisa

This is *HUGE* 📌👏👏👏 And because the reviewing process in [@eLife](#) is very effective, leading to one well articulated and "to the point(s)" consensus review, the potentially ever-long, verbose review that nobody wants to read, will not clog the publication. Excellent!

Simon Mitchell
@SiFTW

This is a cool idea and definitely the right direction. I worry a little about the power this gives to editors. The decision to desk reject needs to be robust and transparent when that's the only barrier to publication.

Ragothaman Yennamalli
@StructBioinfo

Replying to [@PracheeAC](#) [@jboerckel](#) and [@eLife](#)

I like this but not so much....it might end up differently in non-usa academic ecosystem. I am bit skeptical. Is that ok to be? 😊

Support from funders

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar of the HHMI website with the logo and menu items: About, Our Scientists, Programs, Education, News, and Diversity. Below the navigation is a breadcrumb trail: Home / News / HHMI Statement in Support of eLife and Open Science Innovation. The article is dated NOV 15 2022 and is categorized under 'Institute'. The main heading is 'HHMI Statement in Support of eLife and Open Science Innovation'. The text of the article states: 'The journal eLife recently announced a new scientific publishing model. Starting in January 2023, eLife will no longer make accept/reject decisions after peer review. Instead, every preprint that eLife sends for peer review will be published on eLife's website as a "Reviewed Preprint" together with an eLife assessment, public reviews, and a response from the authors. This means that eLife authors – not editors – will decide whether and with what revisions an eLife article will be published. HHMI enthusiastically supports eLife's new model. As one of the founding members of eLife that continues to provide financial support, we stand with scientific leaders who recognize that publishing must change, and that now is the time. If we're to fulfill the public promise of science – new knowledge to benefit all – we need to share research, including scholarly peer reviews, openly. We need to innovate in ways that prioritize research progress and quality of peer review over journal selectivity and'.

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Hannah Hope
@hjhope

Within our grant applications we ask for research outputs - a peer reviewed preprint is one of those.

The model provides a route to complying with our open access policy and thus Wellcome funds for open access continue to be available for publishing with eLife.

5:30 PM · Nov 9, 2022 · Twitter Web App

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CHEN TIANQIAO & CHRISSE INSTITUTE

BILL & MELINDA GATES foundation

Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation

Thank you

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